

SPINMATE

Scalable and Sustainable Pilot Line based on innovative manufacturing technologies towards the industrialisation of Solid-State Batteries for the automotive sector

D1.4 Gender Equality Action Plan

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Glossary and Abbreviations

GEP	Gender Equality Plan
EC	European Commission
R&I	Research and Innovation
EU	European Union
SSB	Solid State Battery

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Executive Summary

This deliverable offers a practical plan to prevent possible gender biases that could take place during the project life time in all gender sensitive activities. This plan focuses on the conception and implementation of policies and actions to drive equal opportunities for all members of the SPINMATE community.

1. Introduction

Since 2010, gender equality was in the top of the list of the EU policy. This later reiterated its strong commitment to this topic and consider it as a human right in the EU Action Plan on Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in Development. Three main goals underpin the Commission's activities on gender equality in Horizon 2020:

1. Encourage the participation of women in the Framework Programme's projects to address these gaps;
2. Surveying a gender balance in decision-making to reach the Commission's target of 40% of the under-represented sex in panels and groups (50% for advisory Groups);
3. Including gender/sex analysis in research and innovation (R&I) content and this deliverable is proof of this orientation of the EC.

Grant Agreement Specifications

The Grant Agreement clearly mentions this issue. Section 1.2.5 was devoted to this topic. That there is an obligation to aim for gender equality: "SPINMATE consortium members have considered gender dimension since the beginning of the proposal preparation stage to identify research and innovation of the project areas in which gender must be analysed and addressed in a differentiated manner. Based on the preliminary gender analysis, the following fields will consider an analysis disaggregated by gender because they are likely to derive in different needs and impact for women and men".

In order to follow this requirement, a series of measures need to be implemented. These measures will be explained in the following section and derived from the project proposal.

Moreover, to be aligned with Belgian law, "the principle of" equal pay for equal work" has long been part of European and Belgian legislation and is one of the cornerstones of gender equality. It is against the law to discriminate against someone based on their gender. An employer must pay the same wage to two employees who carry out work of equal value with the same characteristics. Despite this principle, there is still a wage gap in practice"¹.

In order to follow this specification, the SPINMATE project has set up a gender approach to encourage and foster gender equality in the project, setting up gender indicators to measure progress toward gender equality and establishing a system for monitoring gender equality.

The SPINMATE project is sensitive to equal opportunities between women and men and will focus its attention on ensuring gender balance during the whole lifetime of the project and its as well. At the level of participants of the project, the gender balance typically depends on the types of activities involved in the project.

This document is split into the following gender balance promotion actions:

1. Equal opportunity policy
2. Gender equality actions
3. Targets to achieve a gender balance in the workforce
4. Improve work-life balance

The deliverable D1.3- Gender equality Plan aims to:

¹ <https://settlinginbelgium.be/en/work-and-retirement/equal-treatment-in-the-workplace>

- Set up a gender approach to promote, foster, and support gender equality in the SPINMATE project;
- Setting up gender indicators, and establishing a system for monitoring gender equality
- Supervise and measure the progress toward gender equality;
- Promote and encourage gender equality within partnerships to ensure both male and female representatives take part in the project activities (such as dissemination events or industry workshops)

2. Gender Equality Strategy and Actions

2.1 Gender Equality Strategy

Equal opportunity policy:

In the SPINMATE project, our strategy is essentially based on providing equal opportunities for all partners. This strategy is based on the following principles:

- Commitment of management: Creating an environment that supports equal opportunities is crucial and a collective effort is required to succeed in this process. Each member of the consortium will be involved in this process.
- Collaboration of all partners: all partners are aware that the equal opportunity policy should be implemented and respected;
- Equal opportunity between women and men: balanced representation of women and men at all levels;
- Ensure that all similarly qualified collaborators have equal opportunity and access to obtain training, and participate in conferences, workshops, and other types of activities;
- Build a gender-sensitive management and a professional culture; and working environment;
- Monitor and evaluate the progress on the execution of the adopted strategy for the Promotion of Gender Equality Plan.

2.2 Gender Equality Actions

The SPINMATE consortium guarantee that the actions listed below will be implemented for the purpose of ensuring and implementing the gender equality plan.

1. Equal opportunities dimension: Human resource management will survey:
 - ✓ The performance management and evaluation, to identify and to evaluate the existence of inequalities issues/practices based on gender and to take actions if necessary;
 - ✓ The forward planning of personnel;
 - ✓ The balance between work and private life.
2. Balanced participation/representation of men and women at all levels of the project:
 - ✓ Equal merit for women and men;
 - ✓ Equal representation/ opportunities in the type of position;
 - ✓ Equal representation in the work packages;
 - ✓ Balanced representation in meetings.
3. Guaranteeing that all similarly qualified candidates have equal access and opportunity regardless of gender, age or disability.
4. Ensuring that all partners make efforts to engage both male and female representatives in the project activities (such as workshops or dissemination events).

3. Gender balance in the SPINMATE workforce

Multiple actions are implemented to achieve gender equality in the workforce. As highlighted above, all SPINMATE consortium are involved in this plan and responsible for the success of this strategy. These actions are illustrated as followed:

- ✓ Equal opportunities for all the candidates and collaborators, regardless of their gender, age, or disability;
- ✓ Ensure the gender balance in the evaluators' panels.
- ✓ The same rules should be applied to collaborators;
- ✓ Ensure that no collaborator is discriminated based on a personal characteristic;
- ✓ Balanced participation of men and women at all levels;
- ✓ Ensure equal opportunities within consortium partners;
- ✓ Survey the GEP by scheduling meetings to discuss balance issues.
- ✓ Encourage women to report abuses and protect them and guarantee the confidentiality of the reporter.

4. Work-life balance

To improve work-life balance, each SPINMATE partner adopts some activities to better reconcile work and private life:

- Team-building activities: to promote and anchor the culture of teamwork as well as break the ice between the workers and to help them to build strong human relationships;
- Create a “common space”, where the collaborators interact with each other and have “mental breaks” when needed;
- Set up an open-space environment and encourage team members to talk and give them the confidence to share their issues (professional or personal issues)
- Organize some coaching sessions for “life improvement and personal development” in order to help the team to share, interact and help each other, but also to put the light on the fact that maintaining the balance between work and life is crucial in order to reach professional goals and to be more efficient at work.
- At beginning of the project and during the general assembly, organize sessions to talk to collaborators about their work-life balance needs;
- Ask for regular feedback from team members regarding the work plan and its impact on them.

4.1 Setting up a Gender equality Plan

In order to implement all the discussed points mentioned above some steps need to be implemented. Those steps will be performed based on the Typical GEP cycle shared by the EC.

4.2 Gender equality Audit

Focusing on the gender balance within SPINMATE project, Table 1 Shows the Ratio of men and women in the consortium.

Table 1 – Gender figures per partner

Partners	Date of Data collection	Number of Women	Number of Men	Role (Men/Women)		
				Management	Technical	Other
ABEE	05/01/2023	7	8	2:1	6:4	0:2
ISCF	10/01/2023	3	4	1:0	4:2	0:1
COMAU	11/01/2023	3	5	1:1	3:2	1:0
TUBS	11/01/2023	4	3	2:0	1:2	0:2
TME	10/01/2023	3	1	0:0	1:1	0:2
CEA	05/01/2023	6	6	0:3	6:1	0:2
CID	05/01/2023	10	3	1:2	2:7	0:1
CICe	03/01/2023	6	4	1:2	3:3	0:1
ARKEMA	01/03/2023	3	4	3:1	0:2	1:0
INEGI	04/01/2023	6	4	1:2	3:3	0:1
IREC	11/01/2023	1	2	0:1	2:0	0:0
CPT	11/01/2023	3	3	1:1	2:2	0:0
INOVA+	01/01/2023	3	3	1:1	2:0	0:2

Table 1 illustrates the ratio of women and men involved in the SPINMATE project per partner. It shows the women-to-men ratio in the consortium is balanced with more than 50% of women (Figure1).

Figure 1 - Overall gender ratio for the SPINMATE project

As illustrated in figure 2, per partner, women empowerment is well implemented in almost all the project levels (managerial, technical, etc.).

Figure 2 - Female/ Male composition in SPINMATE project per level

The SPINMATE consortium reveals a well-balanced distribution of genders also at the managing level of the project, with 55% of WP leader/ co-leader positions covered by women and with 5 out of 13 Executive Board Members being female scientists (Table 2).

Table 2 – Managing roles sorted by gender in the SPINMATE project

Role	Total	Women (%)	Men (%)
WP leader/co-leader	9	5 (55.5%)	4(44.5%)
Executive Board Member	13	5(38.4%)	8(61.6%)

At the service/ technology provider level, we have almost a gender balance for industrial partners but for R&D partners together some actions should be taken to increase the involvement of women in the technical side of the project.

Table 3 – Overview of technology providers gender distribution

Role	Total	Women (%)	Men (%)
Industrial Partners			
Raw material supplier (ARKEMA, CPT)	6	50%	50%
Software for LCC and LCA (INEGI)	2	0	100%
LCA and LCC assessment (INEGI)	4	75%	25%
Tool manufacturer (COMAU)	8	37.5%	62.5%
Battery end user (TME)	2	50%	50%
Cell manufacturer (ABEE)	3	33.33%	66.6%
R&D Partners			
CICe, CID, CEA, ISF, IREC, TUBS	33	39.40%	60.60%

5. Conclusions and Future actions

So far, the SPINMATE consortium is noticeably balanced and several actions have already been taken for ensuring gender equality during the open call selection process.

As highlighted during the kick-off meeting and clearly mentioned in **section 3.2.1** in the grant agreement, in this regard, direct actions need to be taken to promote a gender equality policy within the consortium. The future actions will be defined based on what was highlighted by the European Commission.

In particular the importance of:

- guiding targets in decision-making bodies, such as leading scientific and administrative boards, recruitment and promotion committees, and evaluation panels, to achieve gender balance in leadership and decision-making positions;
- monitoring, with appropriate indicators, the implementation of gender policies, and actions within the consortium;
- gender awareness-raising and capacity-building tools
- flexible and family-friendly working conditions and arrangements for both women and men;

The evaluation of gender balance within the consortium will be performed and documented on an annual basis in terms of:

- the percentage of successful female applications to the SPINMATE open calls.
- the percentage of women in senior-level positions.
- Discussions/ roundtables on gender balance will take place during the general assembly meetings to offer a dedicated space for women to discuss and exchange experiences.
- Participation to special sessions on gender parity will be encouraged and supported by the project.
- A gender-balanced participation at internal meetings and workshops as well as at external conferences and exhibitions will be promoted.
- A part of the activities of WP9 will essentially be supporting the dissemination of scientific results and the creation of an international network of collaboration for both male and female scientists.
- Moreover, during WP1 any issue related to gender balance will be pointed out and discussed.
- A 1-day workshop could be organized to discuss gender balance to define actions to be taken especially for those members where the representation of women is still limited.